

Dynamic Wildfire Risk Modelling

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Summary

This paper describes a framework for modelling the *in situ* risk associated with wildfires in order to inform on their immediate local management and longer term risk mitigation strategies. It positions the work within the wider set of risks associated with wildfire (ignition, fuel load management, process models) before describing the components of a model risk, that is parameterised with static landscape scale components (topography, land cover, soil type) and dynamic factors related to weather (soil moisture, relative humidity, wind).

KEYWORDS: Risk, Wildfire, Weather

1. Introduction

Wildfires (WF) are an increasingly important issue for the fire and rescue service (FRS). Current FRS assessments of WF risk -- frequency and intensity -- are based on historical precedents and experience and sometimes do not reflect the impacts on wildfire risk of ongoing climate changes in and associated weather patterns. Wildfire frequencies have increased as was seen in the UK which faces a growing threat from the proliferation of wildfires and other outdoor vegetation fires caused by planetary warming, drought, extreme weather and other dramatic effects of climate change (El Garroussi et al, 2024). England officially experienced four times more wildfires during the summer heatwave of 2022 than in the same period in 2021 (BBC News, 2022). While the risks of seasonal upland moor fires are well known, the 2022 heatwave generated a relatively new phenomenon of lowland wildfires spreading into urban settlements. More than 60 homes were destroyed in a series of simultaneous wildfire-urban interface fires in July 2022 that threatened to overwhelm FRSs across the country. Specific challenges include the increased frequency of outdoor fires during lengthening fire weather periods that, when combined with wildfires, threaten to overrun FRSs.

The threat of dangerous vegetation fires in the UK is strongly related to the amount and composition of biomass fuel that is becoming available as previously moist vegetation dries out. Historically wildfire risk has been considered an upland problem. However, they are increasingly found in lowland areas due to climate changes (Carnicer et al 2022) and are spreading to settlements. In this context, FRSs are increasingly concerned about their ability to quantify changing wildfire risk and to understand their options for managing risks locally when wildfires occur, and in their advanced planning of risk mitigation. The National Fire Chiefs Council (NFCC) and FRSs are now deeply concerned that current assessments of wildfire risk frequency and intensity do not reflect recent changes in climate and weather patterns. The FRS urgently need new evidence and more advanced analytical tools that better capture wildfire risk to both support their operational preparedness and mitigation activities and build urban resilience to the risks of UK wildfires. This paper describes a framework to undertake that.

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2. Background

There are three main types of risk associated with wildfires that are commonly considered in order to be able to mitigate or manage them:

- Ignition risks – the risk of a wildfire starting. Catry et al (2009) outline the factors associated with ignition.
- Combustion or Fuel load risks – planning the landscape to manage the losses from large fires. This is described in Oliveira et al (2016).
- Response risks – the ability of the FRS to manage the wildfire. In the UK, current policy expects FRSs to prevent wildfire incidents from becoming extreme events (Parliamentary Office of Science & Technology, 2019).

There are a number of considerations associated with each of these. In the UK ignition risk is related to visitations patterns on landscapes that have high fuel load and low moisture content, where the potential for accidental ignitions from BBQs, discarded cigarettes etc is greatest. Dixon and Chandler (2019) found accidental ignition to be highest on the upland fringes close to settlement areas, but anecdotally many fires are reported to be started intentionally by arsonists, in remote and unpredictable locations. Fuel load risk has been modelled in a number of ways, with some recent work using remote sensing to quantify seasonal changes in vegetation dry matter and thus generate spatially and temporally distributed measures of risk (eg Gale et al, 2021). These can be readily evaluated using classic GIS overlay to weight and combine layers related to the different components of risk (eg Romero-Calcerrada et al 2008) and with participatory approaches (eg Bartolucci et al 2022). In the UK, a number of agencies with landscape remits have commissioned reports describing the increasing risk and impacts of wildfire, with specific overarching priorities: the National Trust (landscape conservation), The Peak District National Park Authority (national park management), Natural England (biodiversity), etc. All suggest mitigation strategies but from their particular perspectives and none from the perspective of the needs of FRSs. The FRSs want to manage ignition and fuel load risks in advance of a fire, but their perception of risk is different. First, many fires are anecdotally reported to be started intentionally by arsonists, in remote and unpredictable locations, obviating much of the value of the ignition risk modelling. Second, their main concern is to be able to accurately predict or model the impact, duration and extent of a given wildfire when it occurs at a given location.

3. Case Study and Approach

When a wildfire occurs, the FRS procedures are to determine the resources they need to control and contain the fire, and any evacuation strategies. To do this, they consider a wider set of factors than those commonly modelled in classic GIS related approaches. Along with fuel load, access to the wildfire and resources (eg local water bodies), they consider relative humidity and wind as critical factors, more so than antecedent rainfall, as a small breeze will dry out any fuel very quickly. These evaluations are made on site by the FRS Control – the officer in charge on the scene – based on their experience and reading of the situation to create a series of time bound plans (2hrs, 6hrs, 12hrs, 24hrs). The FRS Control would like to use a tool able to capture the landscape factors and the weather related dynamics specific to a wildfire time and location to support such on-site decisions.

The approach taken is to develop a spatial decision support tool that contains the usual landscape scale environmental factors related fuel load (topography, soil type, land cover, etc), but that also captures dynamic measures that will drive the wildfire (antecedent rainfall, current relative humidity, wind strength and wind direction etc), and incorporates static layers related to vulnerability and exposure (human settlement, roads, etc). The FRS prioritise life, then property then the environment, and these interacting components are used to evaluate the nature of the risk to life etc when a fire starts, how to manage that fire immediately and to determine strategies to improve the management of that fire. This paper describes a framework to determine the probable extents of a wildfire, at a given location, given the spatial distribution of local static (landscape) factors and dynamic factors (wind speed and strength, soil and vegetation moisture and relative humidity), over a series of time windows. The tool accounts for interactions between different parameters contributing to WF risk and rate of spread. For example, positive slope (i.e., uphill) in the direction of wind contributes to higher risk scores and faster rates of

spread.

4. Method and Results

The wildfire risk mapping tool combines spatial data layers, covering Marsden Moor in the peak district broadly between Manchester and Huddersfield, resampled to a 25m grid. These are described in Table 1. The user interface has 3 components:

- 1) An interface for users to set preferential weights for each data layer.
- 2) A map of underlying wildfire risk generated from a classic weighted linear combination of the weighted layers (Carver, 1991) as shown in Figure 1.
- 3) An interactive map, that maps the fire extent when a user clicks on a location, after having set wind direction and speed.

It is the last of these that is novel and that starts to provide information to meet the need of the site by the FRS Control. To map the fire extent, a probabilistic cellular automata (PCA) approach that accounts for dead fuel moisture content, wind speed and slope in the direction of spread is followed (Trucchia et al., 2020). It is constructed as follows. First an initial extent (cells) of likely wildfire fire burn is determined based on the underlying conditions: slope in the direction of wind and fuel load from land cover and peat, parameterised (weighted) by wetness from antecedent rainfall over the last 10 days and relative humidity. Next the initial spatial model of risk extent over a given time is adjusted (extended or decreased in different directions depending on the slope, and exposure fires spread up slopes quickly) and wind direction. The final step is to work with the FRS to explore the validity of the interactive map tool to improve its performance and its ability to model FRS Control heuristics and rules of thumb.

Table 1 Data layers used in the risk mapping tool and their sources.

Data Layer	Source and Date
Rainfall volume	Environment Agency Rainfall API (EA, 2024)
Wind speed and direction temperature and humidity	MetOffice Datapoint API (MO, 2024)
Landcover	UK Land Cover Map (CEH, 2021)
Peaty soil	Peaty Soils Location (Natural England 2023)
Lidar Composite DTM	EDINA LIDAR (Digimap, 2023)
Public roads	OS Open Roads (Digimap, 2023)

Figure 1: Snapshot of the classic weighted linear combination wildfire risk dashboard

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Biographies

Abdelrahman Ibrahim (Hegazy) is an applied urban research professional. Academically trained in urban studies and data science. He has seven years of experience in addressing urban inequalities in data scarce contexts with a particular focus on urban accessibility and is currently a Data Scientist at LIDA.

Steve Carver is Director of the Wildland Research Institute. He has worked extensively on the development of wild land mapping and evaluation methodologies and has tested and applied these across a variety of locations and spatial scales including Scotland, England, Britain, Europe, and North

America.

Stuart Hodkinson is a critical urban geography, brought into the realm of wildfires through his research into fire mitigation and planning in the context of large social housing such as Grenfell Tower. He has worked closely with the WYFRS on this and other topics.

Lex Comber's first GISRUK (and peer-reviewed publication) was in York in 2000. He works in all areas of spatial data. Recently he has extended methods for spatially varying coefficient modelling using GAMs and is working with bioinformaticians to incorporate spatial analysis and geocomputation methods within genome and spatial transcriptomic analyses. He's nearly 60 you know!